

To Assess the Correlation between S-Adenosylmethionine Level with Severity of Hepatitis B

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Abstract:

Introduction: Hepatitis B adds to the disease burden due to increased number of cases rising from past decade and is associated with increased morbidity and mortality. S -Adenosylmethionine regulates the cellular proliferation and plays an important role in the early diagnosis of Hepatitis B associated liver disease.

Objective: To assess the correlation between S-Adenosylmethionine (SAM) levels with severity of Hepatitis B and to correlate S-Adenosylmethionine levels with Aspartate aminotransferase, Alanine aminotransferase and alkaline phosphatase.

Methodology: A total of 118 Hepatitis B positive serum samples were collected from Microbiology laboratory from a tertiary care hospital. Blood samples of 5cc in plain tubes were collected from all patients. The serum was separated by centrifugation method and stored at -80⁰ C until S- Adenosylmethionine assay was done by Enzyme Linked Immunosorbent Assay (ELISA) technique and the values will be correlated with Aspartate Aminotransferase (AST), Alanine transaminase (ALT) and Alkaline phosphatase (ALP) levels of the patients.

Result: Out of 118 Hepatitis B positive patients, 74 patients had normal AST , ALT and ALP levels, whereas 32 patients have deranged AST and ALT levels of more than 45 IU/L and 50 IU/L respectively and 12 patients had deranged ALP levels of above 140 IU/L. In patients with deranged Liver function test (LFT), SAM levels by ELISA showed an increase in concentration in 20 patients (P = 0.03), whereas 22 patients had normal levels of SAM (P < 0.05). In 75 patients with normal LFT, SAM levels were within the normal range.

Conclusion: The serum S -Adenosylmethionine levels can be correlated with the severity of Hepatitis B associated liver disease and it can be a potential non-invasive marker which helps in diagnosis of the patients.

Keywords: Hepatitis B, Chronic liver disease, ELISA, Liver function test, S-Adenosylmethionine.

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Introduction

Hepatitis B is a viral infection that majorly affects the liver and has the capability of causing both acute and chronic liver disease [1]. This virus is most commonly transmitted when a person comes in contact with the blood or body fluids during sexual intercourse with an infected partner, vertical transmission from mother to child during birth or at the time of delivery or through needle stick injury from an infected person blood or body fluids [1].

Hepatitis B adds to the disease burden due to increased number of cases rising from past decade and is associated with increased morbidity and mortality [1]. According to WHO 254 million people are living with chronic Hepatitis B infection by the end of 2022, with approximately 1.2 million people developing new infections every year [1]. Hepatitis B infection resulted in an approximately 1 million deaths

by 2022, mainly due to chronic liver diseases such as cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma [1]. S-adenosylmethionine is an essential methyl donor in humans, which plays a major role in methylation reaction and is also involved in many biochemical reactions [1]. Liver is the primary site for the metabolism of S-adenosylmethionine [2]. Since the alterations in methionine metabolism occurs in humans with chronic liver diseases which includes hepatitis, liver cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma which helps to know about the disease progression [2]. S -Adenosylmethionine also regulates the cellular proliferation [2]. S Adenosylmethionine also plays an important role in the treatment modality of liver cirrhosis, as it increases the survival rate of the patients [2].

Materials and Methods

The prospective cross-sectional study was conducted in the Microbiology laboratory at a tertiary care hospital, where Hepatitis B positive samples were collected. Positive serum samples were collected from patients who are 18 years and above, who are HBV positive with/without pre-existing liver disease and may or may not be on treatment. Blood sample of 5cc is collected in a plain tube and the serum will be separated by centrifugation method and stored at -80°C until the assay is done.

The study was conducted from January 2024 to April 2024, after obtaining Ethical clearance from Institutional Ethics Committee, where 118 serum samples were collected from the Hepatitis B positive patients, which were sent to Laboratory for testing.

The data collected will be analyzed statistically using descriptive statistics namely mean, median, standard deviation, percentage wherever applicable. P value <0.05 will be considered statistically significant.

Preparation of sample and reagents: Positive Serum samples should be centrifuged for 10-12 minutes at 1000 g at 4°C , should be aliquoted into cryovials and stored. The samples can be stored at $2-8^{\circ}\text{C}$ for a month or can be further stored at -80°C for up to three months. The serum samples should be diluted 2- to 10-fold with PBS containing 0.1% BSA immediately before performing the ELISA.[12]

SAM Conjugate Coated Plate: Determine the total number of wells to be used in prior and dilute the SAM Conjugate in the ratio of 1:100 in Phosphate buffered saline (PBS). To that add 100 μL of 1X SAM conjugate to each of the well. Overnight incubation should be done at 4°C . The diluted SAM conjugate has to be removed, by gently dapping the plate onto paper to remove excess fluid. Wash the wells 3 times with 200 μL of PBS and gently blot on paper to remove excess of fluid. 200 μL of Assay Diluent to be added to each well and kept in room temperature for an hour. Store the plate at 4°C until assay is ready to begin.[12]

Anti-SAM Antibody and Secondary Antibody Horseradish peroxides (HRP) Conjugate: Dilute Anti-SAM Antibody and the Secondary Antibody HRP Conjugate in the ratio of 1:500 and 1:1000 respectively with Assay Diluent, this dilution have to be made immediately before use.[12]

Procedure:

All the reagents should be bought to room temperature, before starting the assay. After the Removal of the Assay Diluent from the plate, add 50 μL of unknown sample or standard to the SAM Conjugate Coated Plate. Incubate at room temperature for 10 minutes. To that Add 50 μL of diluted Anti-SAM Antibody to each well. Incubate at room temperature for an hour on an orbital shaker.[12]

Microwell strips were washed 3 times with 250 μL 1X Wash Buffer per well, using an ELISA washer. Add 100 μL of the diluted Secondary Antibody HRP Conjugate to each tested well. Incubate at room temperature for 1 hour. Repeat the washing step again. Add 100 μL of Substrate Solution to each well, including the standard and blank wells.[12]

Incubate at room temperature for 2-30 minutes. Enzyme reaction is stopped by adding 100 μL of Stop Solution to all wells. Results were be read immediate. The absorbance reading of each microwell was taken by using 450 nm spectrophotometer as the primary wave length.[12]

The SAM values obtained from the ELISA, were correlated with the Aspartate aminotransferase (AST), Alanine aminotransferase (ALT) and Alkaline phosphatase (ALP) levels of the patients, to know the association of severity in Hepatitis B infected patients.

Results

Out of 118 Hepatitis B positive patients, 80 were male patients and 38 female patients, among them 74 patients had normal AST, ALT and ALP levels, whereas 32 patients had deranged AST and ALT levels of more than 45 IU/L and 50 IU/L respectively and 12 patients had deranged ALP levels of above 140 IU/L.

In patients with deranged LFT, SAM levels by ELISA showed increase in concentration in 20 patients ($P = 0.03$), whereas 22 patients had normal levels of SAM ($P < 0.05$).

In 75 patients with normal LFT, SAM levels were within the normal range.

The results showed increase in SAM levels in 20 HBV positive patients with deranged liver function tests, which may be due to an underlying liver disease, which needs to be further investigated.

Graph 1: The linear Standard curve of ELISA for the concentration measurement of S-Adenosylmethionine in serum samples. The linear equation is $y = -0.0908134x + 2.73874$ with $R^2 = 0.952$

Figure 1: 96 well protein binding ELISA plate after adding substrate solution

Discussion

Our study included 118 HBV positive patients, who had met the inclusion criteria, of which 20 patients with deranged LFT had increased SAM levels, indicating presence of chronic infection with any underlying liver disease, which needs to be further correlated with clinical and radiological findings. Assessing SAM levels in HBV positive patients can be used as a non-invasive marker for early diagnosis, which will improve the prognosis for the patient. Limitation of this study is that normal healthy individuals (HBV negative patients) were not included in the study. However, Clinical importance of circulating SAME levels in patients with positive HBV infection still remains unknown, as there are not many studies regarding this. Different methods to determine SAME levels includes, UV rays for Red blood cells or tissue, it is not used nowadays due to

low sensitivity [2]. Another method is by Fluorescence detection, which has high sensitivity by is time consuming [2]. SAM levels can also be detected by ultra-performance liquid chromatography (UPLC) with tandem mass spectrometry [2].

Ting Li et al conducted a cross-sectional study at Zhongnan Hospital of Wuhan University from January 2012 to December 2013 where plasma samples of 130 patients were collected who were Hepatitis B positive, patients with cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma and normal patient as controls were also included. The results showed that age, HbsAg, serum levels of Aspartate aminotransferase (AST), Alaline aminotransferase (ALT), albumin were significant variables that were correlated with the plasma level of SAM. The study concluded showing a significantly lower S- Adenosylmethionine levels in blood of patients with Hepatocellular Carcinoma

and increased SAM levels were seen in patients with Chronic Hepatitis B infection. The plasma S-Adenosylmethionine (SAM) levels were correlated positively with the severity of Hepatitis B associated liver disease and it might be a potential non-invasive marker which helps in further diagnosis and treatment [2].

Conclusion

Hepatitis B infection if left untreated can cause chronic infection, fulminant hepatitis and can also lead to development of hepatocellular carcinoma [1]. There are not many evidences available to prove that circulating levels of S-adenosyl methionine are involved in the development of liver cirrhosis or hepatocellular carcinoma in hepatitis B positive patients. S-Adenosyl methionine can also be used to treat patients with Hepatitis B associated liver disease [2]. The serum S-Adenosylmethionine levels can be correlated with the severity of Hepatitis B associated liver disease with further comparison to other parameters such as liver function test, liver biopsy, Ultrasound scan. SAM can be used as a potential marker which might help in early diagnosis of liver disease in hepatitis B positive patients, which can reduce morbidity and mortality.

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